

CORROSION EFFECTS ON E-GLASS FILAMENTS, BUNDLES,

AND THEIR ALIGNED SHORT-FIBER COMPOSITES

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Abstract

This work investigates the corrosion effects on E-glass filaments, bundles, and their aligned short-fiber composites. The corrosion of filaments has a significant effect on their Weibull scale parameter but not the shape parameter. The bundle strength degrades rapidly with the increase in the duration of immersion in $1N H_2SO_4$. The corrosion effects on the load-strain curves of E-glass bundles cannot be adequately predicted by the existing statistical theories. In the case of aligned E-glass short fiber composites, crack arrest effects are found when specimens are tested in air. When tested in $1N H_2SO_4$, the fracture of composites obeys linear elastic fracture mechanics. The relationship between crack propagation rate and stress intensity factor has been established.

1. Introduction

In view of the rapid development of composite technology in consumer, automobile and aerospace industries, it is crucial that the durability, especially long-term properties, of fiber composites be adequately assessed.

Glass fiber composites have been used in industry for a much longer period of time and wider applications than graphite, boron, and kevlar fiber composites. For example, glass fiber composites are fabricated into pipes, tanks, and other equipments in chemically corrosive environments. The typical structures of these applications are composed of two integrally bonded layers; the inner chemical resistant layer is made of chopped glass fiber mats with high resin content (90%), and the outer layer consisting of woven fiber layer provides the necessary strength [1]. Such materials possess good chemical resistance and cost less than the stainless steel alloy.

Corrosion effects result in the degradation of stiffness, strength, and resistance to fracture, fatigue, creep and impact loading. Since it is difficult to achieve a permanent chemically resistant material, the failure time of a structure is a major objective of stress corrosion studies. Since the properties of fibers dominate the performance of composites, the corrosion effects on both the E-glass filaments and bundles as well as their aligned short-fiber composites are examined in the present research.

Many kinds of glasses are sensitive to aqueous solution [2-5]. E-glass fibers are subjected to spontaneous cracking after an incubation period both in water and acid. Residual stresses are the major cause of fiber cracking, which can propagate along the axial, radial and spiral directions. Spaude [6] reported that the drawing speed of glass fibers affects their cracking formation rate.

Polymer matrices for composites usually possess good chemical resistance, and protect the fibers from the corrosive environment. Aveston and Sillwood [2] found that a gel-coating on the specimen only delays but does not eliminate the corrosion effects. Register [1] reported that composites with chemically resistant polyester resins show a lower permeation under corrosive environment immersion than those with normal resins and thus retain the properties better. Matrices absorbed with environmental solutions show volume change as well as weight gain. Consequently, residual stresses are often induced at the interfacial regions. The combination of residual stresses and the permeation of corrosive solution leads to the local stress corrosion effects at the fiber/matrix interface. Chemical and physical bonds are degraded under severe corrosion; voids can be formed on the interface and then the corrosion effects become irreversible. Hogg and Hull [7] found when the test condition is changed from corrosion to stress corrosion, composites of tougher resins have better properties than those of more chemically resistant resins. They concluded that the toughness of a resin is as important as its chemical resistance in assessing the properties of composites under stress corrosion environment. This is because composites with lower toughness resins can produce microcracks more easily, and the corrosive agent can approach the fibers faster through these microcracks and cause more severe degradation.

2. Experiments

The present experiments include three parts:

a. Filament Tests

Filament tests form the basis for the study of the strength variability of fibers. All the filament samples are removed carefully from an Owens-corning E-glass bundle (Type 456, 800 filaments) and are in 30 mm gauge length. A modified ASTM D3379-83 method is adopted and filaments are tested on the Instron 1125 Testing Machine with 2.5 mm/min cross-head speed. Three cases are examined:

Case I, filaments without corrosion effect,

Case II, filaments with 16.5 hours pre-immersion in 1N H₂SO₄ acid, and

Case III, filaments with 66 hours pre-immersion in 1N H₂SO₄ acid.

b. Bundle Tests

The E-glass bundle (800 filaments) samples are prepared by two center grooved fiber-glass end-tabs and are in 30 mm gauge length. All the tensile load-strain curves of non-preimmersed bundle samples show sharp rises in the beginning; their maximum loads have coefficient of variation (c.o.v.) between 25% and 29%. Thus, the sample preparation method is acceptable. The bundles are also tested with different pre-immersion periods in 1N H₂SO₄.

c. Composite Tests

Twelve cross-ply aligned short-fiber E-glass composites fabricated by PERME (Propellant, Explosive and Rocket Motor Establishment) of U.K. are tested under both air and stress corrosion environments. The preprags contain aligned 3 mm E-glass fibers with Ciba-Geigy Fiberdux 914 modified epoxy as the matrix. Manders and Chou [8] examined the fiber mis-orientations by an optical microscope and found the root-mean-square of fiber mis-orientation to be 6.8° in the plane of lamination and 2.4° perpendicular to that plane.

After cured for 60 minutes at 120°C and 100 minutes at 175°C with a 3°C/min heating rate under 0.59 MPa (85 psi) pressure, the composites are cut into ASTM E399-83 compact specimen geometry. The specimens are 50.8 mm wide and 2.36 mm thick. Because the machined crack tip is not sharp enough and crack initiation by fatiguing may cause delamination at crack tip, a stress-corrosion-crack-initiation method, which takes about 90 minutes, is used to initiate the natural crack. Thus, consistent results can be obtained through the whole crack propagation process. The ratio of initial crack length to specimen width is 0.33. A guide fixture is used to constrain the specimen and to prevent twisting of the thin specimens (Fig. 1). Specimens are tested under a dead weight, and the crack propagation can be measured through a 60X stereo microscope which is set on a traversing stand (scaled in 0.01 mm accuracy). A layer of chemically resistant grease is applied on the polished surface so that the optical measurements are made easier and more accurate. The following cases are examined:

Specimen A, tested in air without pre-immersion;

Specimen B, tested in 1N H₂SO₄ without pre-immersion;

Specimen C, tested in 1N H₂SO₄ with 960 hours pre-immersion; and

Specimen D, tested in 1N H₂SO₄ with an 18% higher initial stress intensity factor than specimen B and without pre-immersion.

3. Results

Figure 1 - Constraint of fixture for stress corrosion test.

Figure 2 - Retention of properties for E-glass filaments in 1N H_2SO_4 .

a. Filament Tests

The results of filament tests are listed in Tables 1 and 2. A comparison of the degradation of their properties is shown in Fig. 2. The common cumulative strength distribution function $F(\sigma)$ based upon the Weibull distribution is given by:

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp[-(\sigma/\sigma_0)^m] \quad \sigma, m, \sigma_0 \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

Where σ is the stress of the fiber, and the constants m and σ_0 are the shape and the scale parameters respectively. Therefore, $F(\sigma)$ also represents the percentage of failed fibers at the stress σ . Considering the gauge length L , the $F_L(\sigma)$ is given by the "weakest link rule"

$$\begin{aligned} F_L(\sigma) &= 1 - [1 - F(\sigma)]^L \\ &= 1 - \exp[-L(\sigma/\sigma_0)^m] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The filament Weibull distributions based on both failure load and failure strength are illustrated in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. The three cases are given in Sec. 2.a. The difference in the Weibull scale parameters among these three cases indicates that the strength of filaments decreases with the increase in the corrosive immersion period. The corrosion effects on the Weibull shape parameter have been investigated according to the method suggested by Thomas and Bain [9]. The results indicate that there are no significant differences among the three cases at the 0.05 level of significance on the Weibull failure-load shape parameter.

b. Bundle Tests

For the bundle test, the load-strain curves are shown in Fig. 5. The degradation of maximum load due to corrosion effects is shown in Fig. 6; it demonstrates that the strength retention decreases as the immersion period increases.

c. Composite Tests

For aligned short E-glass fiber composites tested in air, Fig. 7 shows the a-t (crack length vs. loading time) curve. The slope of the curve indicates crack propagation rate. There is no unique crack propagation rate for this case; it decreases and increases three times in the whole process. Figs. 8 and 9 show the failed specimen and fracture surface respectively; the pulled fiber bundle is the main feature of fracture.

Fig. 10 shows the results for the same composites tested in 1N H_2SO_4 . The a-t curve (A) for the specimen tested in 1N H_2SO_4 with 960 hours pre-immersion is very similar to that of the specimen without pre-immersion (B). The curve (C) of Fig. 10 shows the a-t relation for the specimen with 18% higher initial stress intensity factor (K_{Ii} is $5.449 MPam^{1/2}$) than specimen B tested in 1N H_2SO_4 . Fig. 11 shows the failed composite specimen tested in 1N H_2SO_4 . The fracture surface due to stress corrosion is rather smooth as depicted in Fig. 12.

Table I. E-glass Filament Testing Results

Property	Case I*		Case II*		Case III*	
	mean	c.o.v.(%)	mean	c.o.v.(%)	mean	c.o.v.(%)
Failure Load (g)	13.38	25.4	11.72	25.7	7.34	28.9
Tensile Strength						
MPa	1462	23.8	1137	28.6	748	27.4
10 ³ psi	212		165		108	
Young's Modulus						
GPa	65.9	17.2	57.6	22.7	57.3	21.15
10 ⁶ psi	9.56		8.35		8.31	
Failure Strain (%)	2.8	22.4	2.5	21.1	1.6	17.8
Diameter (μm)	10.7	10.4	11.4	12.9	11.2	13.7
No. of Specimen	68		73		66	

* Case I: without pre-immersion

* Case II: Pre-immersed in 1N H₂SO₄ for 16.5 hours

* Case III: Pre-immersed in 1N H₂SO₄ for 66 hours

Table II. Weibull shape and scale parameters of 30 mm E-glass filaments

Case	Property	Shape parameter	Scale Parameter
I.	Load	4.23	14.64 (g)
	Strength	4.11	1632 (MPa)
II.	Load	4.19	12.89
	Strength	3.84	1291
III.	Load	3.89	8.45
	Strength	4.14	850

Figure 3 - Weibull distribution chart based upon failure load of E-glass filaments.

Figure 4 - Weibull distribution chart based upon tensile strength of E-glass filaments.

Figure 5 - Tensile load-strain curve of E-glass bundles: (A) without corrosion, (B) and (C) with pre-immersion in 1N H₂SO₄ for 16.5 and 66 hours respectively.

Figure 6 - Comparison between corrosion and stress corrosion effects on E-glass bundles.

Figure 7 - Crack growth curve for short glass fiber composites tested in air.

Figure 8 - Failed short glass fiber specimen tested in air.

Figure 9 - Fracture surface of short glass fiber composites tested in air.

Figure 10 - Crack growth a-t curves for short glass fiber composites in 1N H₂SO₄: (A) without pre-immersion, (B) with pre-immersion for 960 hours, and (C) with higher K_{Ii} .

Figure 11 - Failed short glass fiber specimen tested in 1N H₂SO₄.

Figure 12 - Fracture surface of short glass fiber composites tested in 1N H₂SO₄.

4. Discussions

a. Filament Tests

Fig. 2 shows that the Young's modulus of E-glass filaments is less sensitive to corrosion effects than tensile strength, failure strain, and failure load. Fiber elastic properties are usually not as sensitive to the presence of defects on the fiber surfaces as fiber strength properties. The long immersion time and hence, the degradation caused by the acid are responsible for the initiation of defects. The chemical reactions with the environment result in change of fiber diameter as shown in Table 2.

The mechanism of corrosion of glass filament in acid solution is attributed to ion-exchange [10]:

Aveston and Sillwood [11] reported that the strength of Cermfil glass fiber composites are immune to acid attack because the fibers are free of aluminum and calcium.

b. Bundle Tests

Fig. 13 summarizes the theoretical and experimental load-strain curves of E-glass fiber bundles. The origin of the theoretical curves are given below. First, curve (B) is obtained by assuming that the filaments of a bundle obey Weibull strength distribution and the weakest link rule, and the cross-sectional area and Young's modulus of all fibers are the same. Then the load-strain relation for bundles of length L can be expressed as:

$$P = N \sigma A = N_0 \sigma A \exp [- L(\sigma/\sigma_0)]^m \quad (4)$$

Where P is the tensile load, σ denotes stress, N_0 is the number of filaments in a bundle, N is the number of surviving filaments at a given load. E is the Young's modulus of filaments, A is the cross sectional area of filaments, and σ_0 and m are the Weibull scale and shape parameters respectively. The maximum load can be derived as:

$$P_m = N_0 \sigma_0 A (L \cdot e \cdot m)^{-1/m} \quad (5)$$

The theoretical and experimental curves are similar at the initial stage and become very different when they approach the maximum. The experimental curve drops sharp beyond the maximum load; this is characteristic to all the bundles tested.

Secondly, Kelly and McCartney's theory [12] which includes the propagation rate of surface flaws is expressed as:

$$P = N_0 \sigma A \exp \{ - [m(\sigma/\sigma_0 L^{-1/m})^{n-2}]^{m/(n-m-2)} \} \quad (6)$$

Figure 13 - E-glass bundle tensile load-strain curves: (A) experimental, (B), (C), (D), and (E) theoretical, (B) based upon Weibull strength distribution, (C) and (D) based upon Kelly and McCartney's theory for $n = 8$ and 16 respectively, (E) based upon filament mean strength.

Here, n is a material constant. This prediction is illustrated in Fig. 13 curves (C) and (D) based on n values of 8 and 16, respectively.

Curve (E) of Fig. 13 is simply based upon the mean strength of filaments, and it is assumed that all the filaments possess the same strength properties. Among all the theoretical curves, the maximum load of curve (E) is closest to that of the experimental result (curve A).

In the derivation of the Weibull strength distribution for bundles, the interactions among filaments are ignored. The theoretical curves B, C, and D match the experimental curve A at small bundle strain; the theoretical maximum loads deviate significantly from the experimental results. On the other hand, the prediction of curve (E) assumes no scattering of filament strength, and it tends to overestimate the bundle strength. Consequently, the maximum load of the bundle lies inbetween the predictions of these two approaches.

The load-strain curves of bundles which are pre-immersed in 1N H_2SO_4 show that the longer pre-immersion time results in slower rise of the curves in the beginning. One possible explanation of this result is that appreciable fiber volume change has occurred as a consequence of the fiber degradation. Both fiber length and diameter could have changed by pre-immersion. Therefore, only the shorter filaments in the bundle are loaded in the beginning. The c.o.v. of the maximum load of bundles is also observed to increase with the period of pre-immersion.

c. Composites

It is well known that cracks in composite materials are often associated with damaged zones which exist in the immediate vicinity of the cracks. The damaged zones tend to reduce and disperse the concentration of stresses at crack tips, and divert the crack extension away from the original crack plane. Therefore, the plane-strain condition in fracture testing is no longer preserved [13].

The requirements for the applicability of linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) are [14]: (1) the crack extends in a self-similar manner; (2) the distribution of stress at the crack tip in the anisotropic material is similar to that in the isotropic cases; and (3) crack propagation occurs in a principal direction of elastic symmetry.

Based upon LEFM, the relationship between crack propagation rate and stress intensity factor is

$$V = \frac{da}{dt} = A K_1^n \quad (7)$$

where $K_1 = \sigma Y a^{1/2}$, V is crack propagation rate, n and A are material constants, σ is the applied stress and Y is the geometrical factor. Eq. (7) means that a higher crack intensity factor results in a faster crack propagation rate. When a crack arrest effect occurs, the crack propagation rate is slower than predicted by LEFM. According to the present observations, crack arrest effects can be categorized into two kinds: (1) For continuous crack arrest effect, the crack propagation either accelerates, maintains a constant speed or still accelerates but at a slower rate than that predicted by the LEFM. (2) For kink crack arrest effect, the crack propagation rate changes suddenly. They are illustrated in Fig. 14.

Figure 14 - Schematic crack length vs. loading time diagram: (A) LEFM, (B) continuous crack arrest, (C) kink crack arrest.

Figure 15 - Crack propagation rate curves for short glass composites in 1N H₂SO₄.

The ends of short fibers are the sites for fiber debonding and pull-out because of the local stress concentration induced fiber/matrix interface failure. Both fiber debonding and pull-out can blunt the crack tip and induce crack arrest effects. If the damaged zone at the crack tip is small, continuous crack arrest effect may occur; if the zone is large, the kink crack arrest effect occurs and the fracture surface is characterized by bundle pull-out, and the crack front may deviate far away from the initial plane.

When short-fiber glass composites are tested in 1N H₂SO₄, the crack tip remains sharp and the crack propagates in a self-similar manner. Thus, it is concluded that LEFM is applicable. Fig. 15 gives the result of crack propagation rate vs. stress intensity factors for the case with or without pre-immersion.

5. Conclusions

- (1) The corrosion effects result in the degradation of E-glass filament strength. The Weibull scale parameter is affected significantly; the Weibull shape parameter is almost not affected.
- (2) A prediction of the tensile load-strain curves of E-glass bundles based upon the Weibull strength distribution coincides with the experimental results only for small strains.
- (3) The corrosion of E-glass bundles degrades the bundle maximum load. The change in filament length due to corrosion may be responsible for the uneven stressing of filaments in a bundle.
- (4) Aligned E-glass short fiber composites tested in air show both continuous and kink crack arrest effects. Fiber pull-out, interface debonding, and bundle pull-out are the main features on the fracture surface. The effects of crack arrest have been identified.
- (5) The fracture of composites in 1N H₂SO₄ satisfies the conditions for LEFM. Relations between crack propagation rate and stress intensity factor have been experimentally determined.

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